

**AFTER GLOBALIZATION, WHAT NEXT? A CRITICAL REFLECTION
ON THE IDEA OF A GLOBAL VILLAGE**

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Abstract: This paper attempts to interrogate the concept of globalization from its nature and components. While most scholarly works had looked at globalization as a process, what the process entails is yet to be aptly comprehended. Following a review of existing conceptual and theoretical positions, the paper exposes the conceptual inadequacies in studies on globalization. This piece sees globalization as a function of Mercantilism (M), Capital (C), Multinational Companies (MNC) and Information Communication Technology (ICT). In other words, Globalization = M + C + MNC + ICT. Thus, globalization is taken to mean an extension of Western imperialism in the exploration and exploitation of human and material resources through the instrumentality of finance capital. The works contends that, while there is no global society but a global economy, the concomitant effects of globalization are being taken to mean the actual substances of this phenomenon.

Keywords: Mercantilism, Capital, Multinational, Corporations, Information Communication Technology, Imperialism, New-Colonialism

Introduction

Globalization has raised mixed feelings in the world as this term seems to entrench a skewed distribution of power and resources. It also seems more abstract than concrete to comprehend as the meaning of this concept has being most times, directed to areas that one can refer to as its consequences. The effects of this phenomenon is seen to be of benefit to the Western or developed countries on one hand and inimical to the progress of the underdeveloped countries making the latter unable to maximize the rich human and natural resources inherent in their environment. To be more explicit, countries that are regarded as third world especially those in Africa, had not been able to maximize the rich human and natural resources for the development of the continent due to the challenges of globalization.¹

Globalization, through the instrumentality of the nation-state, has raised the consciousness of disparities and differences amongst peoples and across territories.²This is basically an irony for a process that is said to be integrative of the various economies of countries of the world. In other words, as the world is seen to be more “global”, there are more awareness about differences in development, divisions on group solidarity lines, armed conflicts and political instabilities across

various regions of the world, to mention but a few.³ Thus, globalization essentially makes us more aware of but maintains inequality amongst and across peoples and countries based on the measurement and evaluation of development in Western terms.

The above issues and others not cited provoked a reflection on the age long conversation of what globalization really is, is the world truly a global village? To what extent is the world a “global village”? Moving forward, this paper attempts to address these issues and more as the paper is structured to look at the concept of globalization, a history of globalization which essentially looks at the various components of globalization as well as the concomitants consequences of globalization and a conclusion.

The Concept of Globalization

The concept of globalization, in the twenty first century, is more of a buzz word in everyday human interactions. This is consequent upon the diverse and robust contributions on the meaning of the phenomenon. The perspective of scholars on the meaning of globalization has mostly being divided on whether it is a process leading to an end or an end in itself.

Albrow and King posited that globalization is a process through which the entire human population is bonded in a single society.⁴ They believe it is an economic process of integration which has social and cultural aspects as well. In other words, globalization could be described as an ongoing process by which regional economies, societies, and culture have become integrated through a globe spanning network of communication and trade.

Giddens described globalization as the “intensification of worldwide social relations, which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are swayed by events occurring many miles away and vice versa”.⁵ From a business perspective, ‘globalization’ becomes ‘glocalization’ as there is a conscious attempt to particularize products and services that are sold all over the world to suit people in different localities. This innovative business strategy is dictated by the developed North over the underdeveloped South.⁶ There are views that argue for the conceptualization of globalization to include other aspects. Thus, Giddens and Alfonso Lopez views are efforts to analyze the concomitant effects of globalization than the concept of this phenomenon which is first of all, economic in nature.⁷ In fact, the economic view is the basic foundation of globalization but is mostly relegated as the basest by scholars who ignored the enormity of this reality.

It must be articulated here that, the economic perspective is the most accurate given the fact that, from the political economic view, the economy is the base upon which other aspects which include the way and manner the society is organized, rules and regulations, religion amongst others are tied to. Ake exposed that, the primacy of societal activities is to satisfy its economic needs.⁸ Put differently, for society to continue to exist, it must meet its economic needs and, to do so, that country must be involved in economic productivity which is the primacy of the theory of economic nationalism of human societies. Thus, state power must be used to further that economic interest while interacting with others. This according to Alexander Hamilton, is the genesis of globalization.⁹

The term has sometimes being used as “economic globalization”.¹⁰ This refers to the collection of national economies to form an international economy through trade, foreign direct investment and capital flows, labour related migration and the spread of technology for the end of capitalist exploitation.

Globalization can be seen as a step towards making the world a global village where everyone does virtually the same pattern of activities with the same significance attached to it. For example, the ‘dollarization and eurolization’ of media of exchange in international trade for payments of goods, services and investment is an attempt to make the exchange of goods and services have a common economic value. The World Bank noted that, while the continued integration of national economies through expanding the flows of goods, services, capital, labour and knowledge is to consolidate globalization process, there will be resistance from local governance structures.¹¹ However, the nomenclature, “economic globalization” is only an attempt to break this phenomenon down to several parts and equate all parts as having equal importance.

The resistance being stated above could be comprehended from two perspectives. The first could be seen in the nation-states’ resistance of the ever growing influence of non-state actors such as Transnational or Multinational Companies in the global economic space hitherto dominated by the former. The ebbs and flows of the World’s economy is seen to be dictated by these firms who have great influence over many aspect of life of countries they operate in thereby, infringing on the sovereignty of nation-states.

The second view on why there have being local resistance is the seeming “double standard” adopted by Western powers in the regulation of trading activities on the international scene. Free trade which the international system advocates is only “rhetoric”. While trade must be free in the underdeveloped South, stringent regulations that do not apply to the North are placed for the South to adhere to before they could access the Western markets. This no doubt, has brought disagreements on the true meaning of the freeness of international trade which is the essence of globalization when the developed world had raised “bars and standards” to protect her industries.¹²

Raghavan asserts that, globalization is also being used synonymously for “Liberalization” and “greater openness” of economies- implying both liberalization of domestic economy and external liberalization.¹³ He believes that, while the liberalization of capital and trade flows is creating a unified international economy, the liberalization of telecommunications, which can bring high quality medical, education and business services to the nook and crannies of the world, will globalize human society itself. Thus, the vehicles for driving globalization to the “holes and extremes” of the world is Information Communication Technology (ICT). This complimented the earlier sea-going vessels, air-going vessels as well as other means that facilitated the movement of information and people from and to places.

Globalization and Capitalism can be seen as obverse side of the same coin. Thus, globalization as an end can be seen in V.I Lenin’s postulation of *Capitalism: The Highest Stage of Imperialism*. Lenin (1917) believes that, capitalism has created (globalization) an unbalanced

international economic system where financial capital.¹⁴ He reiterated that, the priority of financial capital was to find new outlets for investments rather than new markets. From this perspective, globalization, which is an imperialist design to control economic activities globally, is a necessary outcome of capitalism. Hobson is of the view that, globalization is the end product of the capitalist dominant motive of imperialism, whose quest was to acquire new markets as well as opportunities for higher returns on investments.¹⁵ In other words, globalization is the end product of the imperialist activities of Western powers to create a world after their economic interests.

Joining this school of thought which avows that globalization is an end is Karl Marx. Marx believes that, capitalism which gave rise to imperialist globalization, was not governed by the aspiration to satisfy human needs, but by the desire and drive to extract surplus from waged labourers. The point to note in the Lenin-Marxist theory¹⁶ is that the ultimate destination or end of imperialism is to ensure the exploration and exploitation of human and material resources through globalization.

The above are positions of some scholars on the idea of globalization. Since there is a very large space for this work to make its contribution to what this phenomenon means, globalization can be defined as the terminal process of collection of national economies into an international economy through the liberalization of trade, foreign direct investment and financial capital flows as well as knowledge by Transnational Companies with the aid of information communication technology for the exploration and exploitation of human and material resources for profit maximization.

It is important to stress that, defining globalization in social, political or other sense other than economic is only trying to define the concomitants effects as the actual concept. The political, social and other dimensions of globalization are essentially to assist in the achievement of the economic processes and ends for the benefit of the developed North who designed the international political economy. Put differently, the first motive of globalization which was orchestrated by Europe, was basically economic in nature.¹⁷

A Brief History of Globalization

Etymologically, the concept, globalization is gotten from the word, *globalize* which refers to the emergence of a world network economic system. An attempt to trace the history of globalization is not a straight jack exercise. This is due to the seeming complex comprehension of the idea and reality of the concept which has also sharpened the perspective on when it started. However, this paper would attempt to historicize globalization by disserting the essential components of this phenomenon. This would no doubt, enable us to appreciate the idea of globalization as an economic phenomenon. To be explicit, there are four ideological stages that conglomerated or accumulated to form the concept under our discourse. In a sequential order, the ideas are;

1. Mercantilism (incorporating imperialism and colonialism) or the motive;
2. Capital (the rise of economic internationalism) or the substance;

3. The emergence of Multinational corporations (the arrival of new competitors to the economic power of the nation states) or the drivers;
4. The introduction of Information Communication Technology (ICT) or vehicle to facilitate trade, investment and business activities in the world.

The summary of the concept of globalization can be comprehended in the expression below;

$$G = M + C + MN + IC$$

Where G = Globalization

M = Mercantilism

C = Capital

MNC = Multinational Corporation

ICT = Information Communication Technology

Mercantilism or Motive of Globalization

The main reason for activating the process of globalization is mercantilism. This is the belief that the state should use its economic strength to further her national interests. This approach is also called economic statecraft or economic nationalism.¹⁸ From this perspective, every nation had at one time or the other, strived to advance her economic position during interactions with others. Put differently, nations and kingdoms before the formation of nation states had being preoccupied with meeting their economic needs throughout human history. To achieve this, they have to annex areas of influence which were directly or indirectly occupied. The two dimensions of the successful implementation of any mercantilist agenda is the manifestation of imperialism and colonialism.

To have a clearer view of the concepts of imperialism and colonialism, it is pertinent to have a working definition. According to Langer,

Imperialism is simply the rule or control, political or economic, direct or indirect of one state, nation or people over similar groups, or ... the disposition, urge or striving to establish such.¹⁹

From the above view, it can be deduced that, even the intentions that have not manifested is considered imperialist since there must be a plan before execution. The point of emphasis is that, globalization is the step by step, well thought out plan to gain total control over the existence of the world especially those in the third world as they are mostly disadvantaged in the international economic system.

Also, the concept of colonialism has been seen as the direct and overall domination of one country by another on the basis of state power being in the hands of a foreign power.²⁰ This saw the interference of the various nations and kingdoms first annexing territories within their locality before striving to dominate other areas outside their regions in order to exploit and control the human and natural resources for their national interests. Thus, in the various continents, you have various nations and kingdoms first superimposing their influence over others in order to control the affairs of such peoples. For example, there was the Benin imperialism in the Niger Delta, Oyo influence in South Western Nigeria and parts of Dahomey,

Kanem Bornu influence in parts of Chad, Niger and North Eastern Nigeria amongst others. In North Africa, ancient Egypt had influence over the Nubian area while the Zulus in South Africa, dominated much of that area. The Chinese did same for the Asiatic territories before the emergence of Japan, Spain and Portugal also had influence over most areas in Europe.

A broad historical understanding of European colonial influence outside Europe can be seen in the African continent dating back to at least the spread of the Roman Empire to North Africa. In 146 B.C., the Carthaginian Empire, which served as the precursor of present day Tunisia, was defeated and occupied by Roman forces.²¹ Other Roman provinces in Africa included Mauritania *Caesarenis* and Mauritania *Tingitana*, which carried the empire westward, across the northern portions of present day Algeria and these areas served as the bread basket of the Roman Empire, producing foodstuff and highly valued olive oil from massive olive tree grooves that remains in evidence. Also, Dike asserted that the only thing that bound Europe to West Africa was commerce. According to him;

“The History of Modern West Africa is largely the History of five centuries of trade with European nations; commerce was the fundamental relationship that bound Africa to Europe”.²²

Dike’s position was also corroborated by Schraeder when he stated that, “the overriding economic purpose of Portuguese exploration was to circumvent Arab traders who controlled Portugal’s overland access to the gold trade of West Africa.”²³ The Dutch were on an economic expedition to India when they had a shipwreck which landed them at the Cape of Good Hope in South Africa. The environmental factors for living and farming were acknowledged to be conducive for them. The rest is history on the issues of Boer migration and settlement in South Africa. The Portuguese exploration to the Americas is not also free from economic motives. These movements ignited the start towards globalization. In other words, the economic interests of the various nations and peoples propelled the start of the first stage.

Nkrumah posits that neo-colonialism represents imperialism in its final and perhaps most dangerous stage. The essence of neo-colonialism is to disguise the real essence of imperialism in which the states especially those in the underdeveloped or developing world, are seen to be independent and have sovereign control over her affairs. However, the reality is that, their economies and political policies are directed from outside.²⁴

Albeit, the major departure point of this work and that of Nkrumah which was an advancement of Lenin’s position, is the identification of information communication technology as the vehicle for conveying information about the global financial market which are sometimes falsified to suit a particular end, especially those of the Western nations who are in control. An example of the use of information communication technology’s role to either promote or ruin the economy of any state is the ‘Nigerian doom’ prediction prior to the 2015 general elections. The Nigerian economy was said be amongst the fastest growing in the world and the largest in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Africa between 2012 and 2015. However, with the forecast that

there would be no Nigerian state after the 2015 elections, the international press and other media agencies amplified this information to the detriment of Nigeria and various foreign investors gradually pulled their investments from the capital market. The elections were conducted and the ruling party, Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), lost with former President Goodluck Jonathan conceding defeat and averting any form of bloodshed and violence. Nigeria had to struggle to stay financially afloat with the economy going into recession. The point being emphasized there is that, the information communication world is owned by the Western capitalist enterprise that use it to sway the economic actions of investors to act in ways they anticipate like never being done before on a global scale. In other words, they can connive with a country to paint it as an 'investor's haven or paradise' where the investments of people are safe as long as they 'play ball' with these international media houses and organizations.

Capital or The Substance of Globalization

The struggle to outwit economic archrivals was in top gear during the motive period. However, to consolidate on one's area of influence requires the accumulation and utilization of capital as an economic advantage in social interactions. Before moving further, let us attempt to comprehend the idea of capital. The meaning of capital has undergone several mutations over the years. Classical or neo-classical economics see capital a factor of production (including land and labour). For Marx, Capital is money used to get or generate more money. Thus, those referred to as capitalists do not see money as a medium of exchange but a substance to be sought.²⁵

Soros posited that, the global economy is characterized not only by free trade in goods and services but even more by the free movement of capital.²⁶ Thus, interest rates, exchange rates, and stock prices which are the basic character of capital, are intimately interrelated in various countries, and global financial markets exert tremendous influence on economic conditions. Foreign direct investments (FDIs) and foreign portfolio investments (FPIs) are major channels of increased financial ties, expanding the growth of investment in other countries. While it is acknowledged that, such international investments have long existed, it has accelerated sporadically since the World War II. According to Rourke, while in 1950, the United States Of America (USA) direct investment abroad was \$11.8 billion, in 1998, that figure had skyrocketed to \$2.1 trillion.²⁷

A major misconception necessary to be cleared is the distinction between capital and money. This can easily be misunderstood as one and same thing. While money is simply used to purchase goods and services for consumption, capital is more durable and is used to generate wealth through investment. Capital includes automobiles, patents, software and brand names. These are items that can be used to create wealth through their production capacities. Capital can be rented out for a monthly or annual fee to create wealth or it can be sold when it is no longer needed.

The point of emphasis here is that, while various societies have their value systems which in some cases are similar to each other, the concept of globalization as advocated in recent times, is to ensure that these systems are made to conform to its exploitative values of psychopathic individualism, aggressive capital accumulation and market fundamentalism which has caused

several challenges manifested in forms related to social, political, economic, etc. A fundamental hidden fact about globalization is that, it does not tell how prosperous everyone would be while preaching “prosperity for all” in its idea of economic liberalism and internationalism through the liberalization of trade evident as capital transactions. However, seeing the damage a “totally” free economic system would have at the long run, John Maynard Keynes believes that, with capitalistic globalization properly managed, it can probably be made more efficient for attaining economic ends without offending various notions of a satisfactory way of life.²⁸

Multinational Corporations: Drivers of Globalization

Multinational corporations (MNCs), which are classified as non-state actors in international relations, are essentially the agents of globalization. It is their activities that have truly made the manifestations of globalization to become a reality. In fact, they are the forerunners of economic exploitation and imperialistic manipulations for their various states. This is why the nation-states are most times, scared of the activities of these non-state actors who the former perceives, as dangerous and might contribute to its doom. Thus, an advocacy for a “United States of the World,” would see the death of the nation-states and the dominant nature of Multinational Companies. It has being referred to as worldwide enterprise, transnational enterprise, transnational corporation, as well as international corporation which have thin lines of differences but same objectives and aims chief amongst which, is to maximize profits in their areas of operations.

An MNC is a private enterprise that includes subsidiaries operating in more than one state. This entails more than just international trading. Rather, it implies ownership of manufacturing plants and/or resource extraction and processing operations including supplying services such as banking, insurance and transportation in various countries.²⁹

Caves see Multinational Companies as Multinational Enterprise (MNE) that controls and manages production establishments-plants-located in at least two countries. The nomenclature of MNEs can be seen in three groups which include: (i) the multi-plant firm that turns out basically the same line of products from its plants in each geographic market, establishing horizontal integration (ii) a multi-plant firm that produces output in some of its plants that serves as inputs to other of its plants, creating vertical integration in its activities (iii) a diversified company whose plants’ outputs are neither vertically or horizontally related to one another.³⁰

Fieldhouse defined MNC as a firm which owns or controls income-generating assets in more than one country.³¹ The exploitative character of MNCs has been sufficiently addressed as outfits that are out to extract surplus value from the activities of workers in underdeveloped countries.³²

All of these companies have established manufacturing plants in many countries. They chose spots where the raw materials or labour is cheapest. This enables them to produce components of their products in different countries as well as assemble factories territories in various continents. Thus, this level of economic global village orchestrated by the MNCs, allows them to view the whole world as the market for their goods which ensures that such goods and services are distributed throughout the world as if there were no national boundaries.³³ However, we must note that there are MNCs are also service provide entities. For example, we have insurance,

telecommunications, banking, pharmaceutical and related industry that are not into direct production of goods but renders services needed in various countries.

From the above exposition, one can infer that, the term, multinational firm is actually a euphemism for nationally originated firms of developed countries. Retaining their total identity in a foreign land might meet a hostile accommodation by the governments and peoples of the various countries it intends to operate in. Thus, these MNCs have to “remake” themselves by allowing some local participation in their activities.

This is done essentially by releasing some of her shares to members of the country it intends to operate in to own as well as the employment of a number of staff from that environment. This however, does mean that the parent company of the MNC does not have majority shares or try to take control of the business and delist or transfer the subsidiary’s major components to a 100 per cent subsidiary, while using such delisted company for other aspect of the business.³⁴

To really underscore the financial power and influence of MNCs, it is imperative to cite the case of one of the biggest companies that had ever existed. General Motors (GM) in 1999, had a Gross Corporate Product (GCP) of \$161.3 billion that was about equal to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Norway (\$152.1 billion), more than twice that of Egypt (\$79.2 billion), more than three times the GDP of Hungary (\$46.6 billion), and 90 times the GDP of Armenia (\$1.8billion). To capture the nature and character MNCs, let us take a look at their evolution to enable us appreciate the dimension this piece has taken.

The evolution of MNCs was a concerted economic readjustment that took place in Europe with the opening of ocean trade routes which was a very important development. However, this was by no means the only factor as others include the growth of population as well as a long and gradual rise in prices or slow inflation. These conditions created a fertile crescent for Europe’s economic changes, signifying the rise of a capitalistic economy and the transition from a town-centered to a nation-centered economic system from about the fourteenth century, attaining maturity when machine industry began to overshadow commerce in the early nineteenth century. Therefore, during the mercantile era, various European governments introduced new policies and regulations, geared towards self-sufficient economies. For example, England, in turning her country into a hive of industry, discouraged idleness, begging, unemployment and poverty by providing incentives for the formation of companies.³⁵ This was intended to develop new crafts and manufactures. Thus, favors and certain advantages were given to businessmen and merchants who provided work for the “poor” and who sold the country’s products in foreign lands. The *English Poor Law of 1601* (which remained in effect though with amendments until 1834) was designed to propel greater productivity and encourage the formation and growth of the private sector in the development of their economy.

Aside the above, governments took steps to introduce new industries. The silk industry was brought from Italy to France under royal protection to the dismay of French woolen and linen interests likewise England which took similar actions. Thus, without government’s support, the “great” merchants or businessmen could not have risen and prospered as had being recorded by history. It is now clear that, it would have been very difficult for individual European merchants

to act by mere private initiative as those trading in distant places needed good amount of capital or regularly had to obtain protection from the home government by arming their ships against alleged pirates and other hostile Europeans whom were out to also further the mercantilist interest of their country.

For easy management and administration of these business concerns, merchants and their respective governments came together to form official companies for the trans-ocean trade which was a step towards globalization. In England, the formation MNCs came from about 1553 with the establishment of a Russian-bound company. While Turkey was said to have followed almost immediately, from about 1600, several companies were operating out of England, France and Holland. These companies had monopoly in areas they operated, were state-sponsored or supported with special rights.³⁶ This is the character of globalization which is essentially from its origins, intended to extract surplus value from areas of influences.

It is expedient to state that, while these exploratory activities of the MNCs continued for centuries through trade and national policies manifested in colonialism, the global economy did not fully evolve until the last decades of the nineteenth century were the international economic system entails all the direct foreign investment, businesses and governments that cross international borders. In the turn of the twentieth century, the burgeoning American industry began to be a force to be reckoned with.³⁷ This saw the rise of the Ford Corporation, General Electric and Otis Elevator amongst others, expanding their operation bases to Europe and created the fear of take-over of European economy. In recent times, several factors hastened the growth of MNCs. Telephones and computer linkages to internet services, has made global financial transactions quick and easier.

Information and Communication Technology: Vehicle of Globalization

The essence of information and communication technology (ICT) is to unify global business communication services. This ensures the merger of telecommunication channels which includes telephone lines and wireless signals, as well as computers which affords the individual to have the various services available to him in one package. Broadly, ICT refers to the technology used to handle telecommunications, broadcast media, intelligent building management systems, audiovisual processing and transmission systems, and network-based control and monitoring functions. Thus, it is used to encompass audio-visual and telephone networks through a single link system.

The one of the underlying reasons for this unification of communication are the large economic incentives being provided through the aggregation of telephone network and computer network systems. In fact, the net worth of the ICT sector has being on the steady rise, estimated at \$3.5 trillion in, doubling every 15 years and increasing at 5% per year.³⁸

The arrival of new technology manifested in the introduction of information systems and the internet, revolutionized the cost of processing and transmitting information as well as the production of sophisticated computers and its related gadgets. While the artificial satellites launched into space in the 1960s aided worldwide communications, the brainchild of linking the globe through worldwide communications was the miniaturization³⁹ of the computer. Indeed,

personal computers have become essential in daily lives and offices as millions of people around the world have access to them. Some of these personal computer devices include telephones, fax machines, photocopiers and video as well as audio cassette players which facilitates real time business activities.

People around the world have access to information from other areas through subscriptions to television news agencies such as Cable News Network (CNN), Al-Jazeera, British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), Voice of America (VOA), African Independent Television (AIT) and others which is now a very lucrative business in the world. Satellite technology enabled television networks to provide common experience the world over, mostly through sports. For instance, an estimate one billion people watched the World Cup in 1994 and three billion people, the 2000 Olympics.⁴⁰ This has propelled the massive flow of finance capital both as investment in the organization of the games and transmission of the sporting activities as well as profits accruable to shareholders of the television companies and host governments, unknown to the vulnerable worldwide.

Concomitant Effects of Globalization

The unintended results of globalization on the international political economy are numerous. This essentially means that, the effect of this phenomenon has snowballed into areas that it had not, in the first instance, set out to achieve. These are manifested in political, cultural and social forms. Let us outline them briefly below.

On the political space, the seeming manifestation of a vertical authority structure that even the most powerful states are gradually being submissive to, are actually in cases that involves “western interest” that they allow such international rules made by intergovernmental organization (IGOs) and international law to be applicable to them. In other words, such international organizations including the United Nations Organization (UNO), are essentially “settling” fora of western conflicting economic interests. The urgent need to form such bodies can be seen in the attempt to have a conflict resolution mechanism after the Berlin Conference of 1884/85 to manage and resolve European economic interests in Africa and other parts of the world. Thus, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, International Court of Justice (ICJ) and other international organizations are not mechanisms to make at par or redistribute the economic resources of the “haves” to the “have-nots” but are actually media of directing the affairs of the non-western countries to their economic advantage.

Still on the political plane, the idea of balance of power in international relations, is actually a euphemism for managing aggressive mercantilist behavior of nation-states which we have identified to be economic in the first instance. This can be seen in Kissinger’s assertion that, American leadership would have to, in the next (21st) century, articulate for her public a concept of national interest and explain how that interest would be served in various parts of the world especially by the maintenance of balance of power.⁴¹ From this perspective, we could infer that the President Donald Trump’s administration is actually serving the interest of the American people before consenting to render any form of assistance to any country. The United States of

America's threat to withhold aid to countries that objected to the recognition of Jerusalem as the capital of Israel is a case in point.

On the social front, there is an attempt to challenge the imposition of American values and norms on the world. Though English language seems to be the lingua franca of the world, there is still a battle to first, maintain territorial language hegemony in western countries as well as fight to change or be at par with the English language as the official language of cross-cultural economic interactions. For example, Ogbogbo noted that, a German airport official would prefer to look for an interpreter to mediate in a conversation with an Ijaw tourist from Nigeria than speak English language with him which is a second language the latter might be conversant with.⁴² This is thus, an attempt to preserve the territorial hegemony of that language from begin dominated in its natural habitat.

The English language can be said to be an "elitist" language in the African continent which is essential for economic transactions between peoples. While the aim of Europeans was not to teach Africans their language in the first instance, their triumph over the peoples of the continent was first essentially the ability of 17th and 18th century European traders and merchants to comprehend African worldwide and personality through the mastering of African languages. Thus, Europeans stooped to learn African languages which aided their victory over the African and other cultures. This would not have been possible without their attempt to satisfy their national self-interest. The concomitant effect of this is that, it has distorted the earlier media of economic interaction in Africa which was tied to kinship and marriage.

As a follow-up to the above, globalization has created, enforced and sustained an "individualistic" world as against a "communal" world. In fact, the African continent is in a state of confusion as regards whether to religiously hold on to western oriented individualism or their pre-contact-with-the-west state of communality. In other words, globalization has created for Africans, a state of socio-cultural crisis than its attempt to unify her with other parts of the world. Thus, as a reminder to our paper title, it is pertinent to ask, which way to go for Africa in the stage called globalization? This is in view of the fact that, the general perceived idea of globalization is to bring solutions than create problems especially on the non-tangible aspects of human culture.

Globalization process has aided the spread of culture which the economic endeavour of any people is part of. The challenge is that, non-humanistic scholars always showcase and emphasize the non-material and non-economic dimensions of culture thereby missing the point that globalization is first, an economic phenomenon before any other consideration.

Conclusion

There is a global economy but no global society.⁴³ The findings of this piece have substantiated that, the economic position is the base upon which the much sorted after global society is taking shape. The main challenge is that, there are contending forces within and without the capitalist West which are bent on hijacking the control of the international economic system. These economic mutiny related activities had to be fought at all fronts including political, religious,

socio-cultural, etc. which are taken to mean that globalization is not economic in the first instance.

The global world has no “international” set rules and regulations for “inter-nation-state” relations. This is because the so called rules and regulations are basically by the West ab initio for the regulation of their activities. Some notable examples are the Westphalia and Versailles Treaties as well as the United Nations Organization which were initiatives of Europe and the United States of America to manage conflicts among themselves. In other words, the global or international system, as it is today, was designed, built and so far, sustained to meet western standards.

Until such a time when the international political arena become democratic to the extent of the security council of the United Nations being constituted by majority votes without undue pressure on “less developed” countries by the superpowers as well as the rules and regulations applied to all without let or hindrance, the manifestation of globalization would continue to be detrimental to the former. This can clearly be understood from George Orwell’s Animal Farm famous line that all nation-states are equal in the age of globalization but some nation-states are more equal than others. Globalization has come to stay and the international system, from the cyclical explanation of history perspective would continue to take different shape in modifying itself at the will of the Western world to continually suit their interest. Whether it would be made to accommodate African and other non-western interests is left for history to account for.

Endnotes

¹Rodney, W. (1972). How Europe Underdeveloped Africa. London: Bogle-L’Ouverture, p.30

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⁶The term ‘developed north’ in development literature is essentially a description of the Western superpowers or developed countries which include, the United States of America (USA), Britain, France, Germany and others considered to be in this group. The term, ‘underdeveloped south’ refers to countries in Africa, South America, the Caribbean’s, and Asia. The above terms are rather fluid as Russia is not considered by some as a developed country in the North despite being a “world power”. Also, the ‘Asian Tigers’ are no more considered underdeveloped countries even though they in Asia. Please visit the websites of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), www.imf.org and The World Bank, www.worldbank.org for classifications. Also see Derek Gregory, et al eds. (2009), “Asia Miracles/Tigers”. *The Dictionary of Human Geography* (5th ed.), Malden, MA: Blackwell; Soros, G. (2004), *The Crisis of Global Capitalism, open society endangered*. New Delhi: Viva Books P. L.

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- ⁸Ake, C. (1980), *A Political Economy of Africa*. Harlow: Longman
- ⁹Cited in Rouke, J. T., (2001), *International Politics on the World Stage*. Connecticut: Dushkin Publishing Group, 5th ed. P389.
- ¹⁰IMF, IMF Survey, September 26, 1997.
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- ¹²For insights on the unequal international trade relations, see Cletus, C. Coughlin, et al (1995), *Protectionist Trade Policies: Theories, Evidence, and Rationale in J. A. Frieden & D. A. Lake (ed), International Political Economy: Perspectives on Global Power and Wealth*. New York: St. Martin's Press. pp. 323-338.
- ¹³Raghavan, C. (2009), *Globalization*. www.twinside.org.in. Accessed 16/03/2010.
- ¹⁴Industrial capital refers to "fixed capital". This could be seen in the investments in industries and infrastructure that takes longer time to yield returns or profits.
- ¹⁵Hobson, J.A., (1902), *Imperialism: A study*. United Kingdom: Cosimo
- ¹⁶The Lenin Marxist theory did not explicitly contribute to the idea of globalization. However, considering globalization as a component of capitalism, one can deduce from the perspective of these scholars that, it is now the highest stage of imperialism
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- ¹⁸Rouke, J. T. (2001), *International Politics on the World Stage*, p.389
- ¹⁹Langer, W. L. (1935), *The Diplomacy of Imperialism: 1830-1902*. New York: Knopf. 2nd ed. 2nd Vols. p.67
- ²⁰Nwankwo, B.C. 1998. *Colonialism and its impact in Africa*. *African Politics*. Emezi, C.E. & Udoh, C.A. (eds). Port-Harcourt. Avis Consult, p.31
- ²¹Schraeder, P. J. (2004), *African Politics and Society: A Mosaic Transformation*. Thomson/Wadsworth, p.50
- ²²Dike, K. O. (1956), *Trade and Politics in the Niger Delta...*, p.1
- ²³Schraeder, P. J. (2004), *African Politics and Society...*, p.51.
- ²⁴Nkrumah, K. (1965), *Neo-Colonialism: the Highest Stage of Imperialism*. London: Thomson Nelson and Sons Ltd. Nkrumah was able to breakdown the condiments imperialist neo-colonialism which includes the international capital's control of the world market, prices of commodities bought and sold in favour of Western monopolies, high rates of interest from the developed countries and other capital institutions, multilateral aid through international organizations such as the International Monetary Fund, the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (known as the World Bank), the International Finance Corporation and the International Development Association etc. which are used to indicate Western oriented development on a global scale to the detriment of these countries. Also see Stiglitz, J. (2002), *Globalization and its Discontents*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company.
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- ³¹Fieldhouse, D. (1995), *A New Imperial System? The Role of Multinational Corporation Reconsidered* in Frieden, J. A. and Lake, D. A. (eds.), *International Political Economy: Perspectives on Global Power and Wealth*. New York: St. Martin's Press.
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